

Nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate: Advantages and inconveniences in consolidating ancient bricks (XII-XIII century)

David Navarro-Moreno ^a, Ana Martínez-Arredondo ^a, Victoria E. García-Vera ^a, M^a Lourdes Gutiérrez-Carrillo ^b, Juan Antonio Madrid ^c, Marcos Lanzón ^a

^a Departamento de Arquitectura y Tecnología de la Edificación, Escuela Técnica Superior de Arquitectura y Edificación, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Campus de Alfonso XIII, 50, 30203 Cartagena, Spain

^b Departamento de Construcciones Arquitectónicas, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería de la Edificación, Universidad de Granada, Campus de Fuentenueva, Severo Ochoa s/n, 18071 Granada, Spain

^c National Center of Reference for Chemical VET, Cartagena, Spain

h i g h l i g h t s

Arabic bricks (XII-XIII century) are studied to propose adequate conservation methods.

The bricks are rich in carbonates and they were most likely calcined at $T < 850$ C.

Diluted $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ nanoparticles are effective solutions and compatible with bricks.

Ethyl silicate produces minimal colour change and reduced water permeability.

Sodium silicate forms hard coatings, but it is prone to cracks and efflorescence.

Abstract

This paper aims to study the strengths and drawbacks of nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate coatings in consolidating heritage bricks. Initial X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and thermogravimetric analyses (TG-MS) showed the bricks are particularly rich in carbonates, although they also contain quartz and minor proportions of halite and gypsum. The consolidants were examined by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM); Optical Microscopy (OM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM); and their effectiveness was tested by non-destructive methods based on colour variation or minimally destructive ones as peeling tests, Shore-A hardness and water permeability tests. The colorimetric properties of bricks were dissimilarly affected by the treatments being ethyl silicate the one that induced the lowest change. It was found that sodium silicate formed hard coatings that were prone to cracks and efflorescence formation after few days of curing. Nanolime and ethyl silicate provided similar consolidation performance, although water permeability was visibly reduced by the latter coating. In contrast, the initial XRD, XRF and TG-MS characterisation of heritage bricks confirmed they are more similar (compatible) to nanolime than the rest of treatments.

Keywords

Calcium hydroxide nanoparticles; Ethyl silicate; Sodium silicate; Ancient bricks; Heritage conservation

1. Introducción

This paper is a preliminary study of heritage materials from the archaeological site of San Esteban (Murcia, Spain), which is currently under restoration (Fig. 1). The site is a medieval quarter dated in XII-XIII century, occupies an area of 10.000 m² and constitutes one of the most significant examples of Andalusi urbanism in Europe. An interdisciplinary research project combines the vision of historians, archaeologists, engineers, conservators and chemists to restore and preserve the site. The excavated remains include several houses, a *funduq* and an oratory among other buildings. The walls are built with faced-bricks and traditional Arabic rammed earth, also known as *Tapial* [1–3].

In restoration works, the use of consolidants represents a suitable strategy to strengthen weak surfaces and delay deterioration processes that often take place in heritage materials. However, some consolidants may produce substantial alteration of original characteristics of heritage materials [4,5]. For this reason, the consolidant-substrate similarity is a crucial aspect to be addressed in the science of conservation.

Fig. 1. Aerial view of the archaeological site of San Esteban (Murcia, Spain).

Limewater is made by dissolving Ca(OH)_2 in water and has been traditionally used to strengthen lime renders, limestone and wall paintings. Nevertheless, limewater treatments may not achieve great penetration depths even when applied on porous substrates. In limestone, for instance, some authors have reported that more than half the Ca(OH)_2 remains in the outer 2 mm [6,7]. Besides, the high number of coats increases the whitening of the surface and limits the practical use of limewater treatments. With the arrival of nanomaterials, limewater is being replaced by nanolime suspensions made of Ca(OH)_2 nanoparticles dispersed in alcohols. The small Ca(OH)_2 particles may penetrate into internal pores of stone, mortars and analogous materials [8–11]. Another advantage of nanolime over limewater is that water solubility of Ca(OH)_2 is low (1.6 g/L at 20 C) [12], whereas the approach of dispersing small particles in alcohols allows us using much higher concentrations. In both cases, the consolidating action is due to carbonation of Ca(OH)_2 leading to CaCO_3 , which is similar to calcareous minerals also made of calcium carbonate [4,10]. In this way, the similarity of nanolime with calcium carbonate-based heritage materials represents a clear strength of the treatment. As a consequence, at least in theory, nanolime may cover a wide range of uses in preserving wall-paintings, artistic surfaces [8,13,14] and building materials like tapial, stone and lime mortars [3,10,15,16]. Yet, the consolidating action is affected by the amount of Ca(OH)_2 dispersed in the suspension as well as the type of solvent and relative humidity of the environment [17–20].

Nowadays, ethyl silicate (TEOS; tetraethyl orthosilicate) is a widespread solution in heritage conservation [21–24]. The hydrolysis of ethyl silicate occurs with release of ethanol (volatile) forming a nanosilica binding phase within the pores (Fig. 2). Contrary to quartz, the deposited silica phase is amorphous and may shrink by suction of the substrate or if it is exposed to dry environments [25]. Besides, the scarce similarity between amorphous silica and certain building materials along with possible colour changes induced by the treatment are reported as possible limitations of ethyl silicate [26,27].

Sodium silicate coatings are water-based solutions with the ability to strengthen porous surfaces and particularly those containing calcium [28,29]. It can be manufactured by hydrothermal reaction between NaOH and SiO_2 giving an aqueous mixture also referred to as water glass. The amount of NaOH in the solution has strong impact on the polymerisation degree of sodium silicate [30]. Jansson et al. found that the formation of isolated SiO_4^{4-} units - or depolymerised species (Q^0) - increases with NaOH concentration as confirmed ^{29}Si NMR and IR spectra. By contrast, an excess of SiO_2 favours Q^1 , Q^2 and Q^3 configurations, in which silicon tetrahedrons are bonded to one, two or three nearby ones, respectively.

This paper aims to study effective strategies in consolidating historical bricks from an archaeological site which is currently under restoration. Preliminary analyses are conducted on original samples by XRD, XRF, TG-MS and microscopy techniques. Moreover, nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate consolidants are compared on the basis of colour change, consolidation performance, stability, water permeability and compatibility features.

Fig. 2. Left: molecular structure of tetraethyl orthosilicate, $(\text{EtO})_4\text{Si}$; Right: 3D view of amorphous silica (SiO_2) structure formed by hydration of $(\text{EtO})_4\text{Si}$ and ethanol elimination (EtOH); Et: $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$; atoms: silicon (beige), oxygen (red), carbon (grey) hydrogen (white).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and samples preparation

The chemical properties of nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate are shown in Table 1. The nanolime suspensions (NL) were synthesised in laboratory ($70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in N_2 atmosphere) using the methodology reported by Madrid and Lanzón [31]. In addition, commercial ethyl silicate (SE) and sodium silicate (SS) were used in the study. The concentration of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was 5 g/L and the suspensions were sonicated in 2-propanol for 10 min at 110 Watts. In addition, commercial ethyl silicate (ES) and sodium silicate (SS) were used in the study. It is worth noting that the studied $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ concentration in nanolime suspensions (5 g/L or 0.5% w/v) is significantly lower than that used in commercial solutions of ethyl silicate and sodium silicate (Table 1). Nevertheless, diluted nanolime suspensions whiten less than concentrated ones and have shown good performance in preliminary studies [3,10,17].

The coatings were sprayed at a distance of 7 cm using an airbrush coupled to a laboratory compressor regulated at 1.3 bar [3,10]. The nanolime treatment was applied in five coats to compensate, at least partially, the low concentration of active component and waiting 12 h in between coats. The ethyl silicate and sodium silicate consolidants shown in Table 1 are ready-to-use commercial products and therefore, no dilution was made. The coated materials were stored in laboratory conditions ($23 \pm 2\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $70 \pm 1\%$ RH) for six weeks to allow the curing reactions to happen.

Table 1. Chemical features of consolidants (nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate)

Feature	NL	ES	SS
Aspect	white	colourless	colourless
Active component	Ca(OH) ₂	(CH ₃ CH ₂ O) ₄ Si	Na ₂ SiO ₃
Concentration, w/v %	0.5	75	26.6 / 8.0 ⁽¹⁾
Coats, n	5	1	1
Solvent	2-propanol	white spirit	water
Density, g/cm ³	0.79	0.95	1.29
Sedimentation (4 days)	negligible	none	None
pH	12.1 ⁽²⁾ / 8.4 ⁽³⁾	NA	12.3
Approx. size of nanoparticles, nm	200–400 ⁽⁴⁾	NA	NA

NA: Not Applicable

⁽¹⁾ Average SiO₂/Na₂O fraction;

⁽²⁾ pH determined in aqueous phase;

⁽³⁾ pH in 2-propanol;

⁽⁴⁾ Measured by TEM from the smallest and largest size of fresh nanoparticles.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. XRD, XRF and TG-MS analyses

The XRD, XRF and TG-MS analyses were carried out on brick fragments taken from the monument (Fig. 3). The fragments were crushed in agate mortar to obtain a fine homogeneous powder and dried at 60 °C until constant mass. The brick minerals were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer in Θ - Θ mode operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. The spectra were registered from 10° to 70° at 0.05° stepping intervals using the PDF4+ diffraction database and DIFFRAC.EVA software. Likewise, the chemical composition was evaluated by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) with a Bruker S4 Pioneer fluorescence spectrometer. Finally, volatile components like CO₂ and H₂O were quantified by thermal analysis (TGA/DSC 1HT Mettler-Toledo) coupled to a quadrupole mass analyser ThermoStar QMS 300M3 (TG-MS). The thermograms were register in O₂ atmosphere using a gas flow and heating rate of 50 ml/min and 10 °C/min.

Fig. 3. a) Detail of brick walls laid by alternative courses of stretchers and headers; b) Original brick fragments used in characterisation tests.

2.2.2. Optical microscopy (OM) and electron microscopy examination (SEM and TEM)

Images at intermediate magnifications (50–200x) were captured with a digital microscope Dino-Lite Edge. The optical microscope was equipped with regulating LEDs, polariser filter and a calibration target for precise adjustment of magnification. For higher magnifications (500–10000x), a scanning electron microscope (SEM) Hitachi S-3500N operating in secondary electrons detection (SE) was used. The examinations were performed in ultra-high vacuum using moderate accelerating voltage (5 kV) at a working distance of 8 mm. The samples were previously dried for 24 h at 60 °C and after that, they were metallised with Platinum to improve collection of secondary electrons (resolution). Besides, the treatments based on nanoparticles were studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) JEOL JEM-1400 Plus at 120 kV using an Orius camera for images acquisition.

2.2.3. Colour variation

The original bricks (XII-XIII century) were available in a limited number and moreover, they showed natural colour variations and external deposits that made colour tests difficult to perform and inaccurate. Hence, in this case, only uniform ceramic surfaces were used to assess with better precision colour alterations induced by the coatings. A spectrophotometer Konica Minolta CM-700d equipped with white calibration plate; aperture setting of 6 mm and 10 angle observer was used in colorimetric tests. The number of coats was the same as than mentioned in Table 1, but the consolidants were applied with micropipette (20 μ L) to achieve uniform deposition. The tests were recorded in the CIE-L*a*b* colour space, in which L* denotes lightness; a* red/green and b* blue/yellow colour. Further tests were recorded in the CIE-L*C*h⁰ system that uses polar coordinates instead of Cartesian ones. In this case, C* specifies chroma

i.e. how bright or dull the colour is; h^0 is hue and L^* remains the same as in the CIE- $L^*a^*b^*$ system. The relationship between C^* , h^0 , a^* and b^* is shown below:

$$C^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}}$$

$$h^0 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{b^*}{a^*} \right)$$

D65 standard CIE illuminant light source was selected to simulate daylight conditions (6504 K) and the overall colour change was evaluated as follows:

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(L_1^* - L_0^*)^2 + (a_1^* - a_0^*)^2 + (b_1^* - b_0^*)^2}$$

Where,

- 1 and 0 subscripts denote coated and non-coated samples, respectively
- L ranges from 0 (black) to 100 (white)
- a is the green (-) to red (+) colour axis
- b is the blue (-) to yellow (+) colour axis

2.2.4. Peeling and hardness tests

The peeling test allows measuring the surface cohesion of porous materials [3,10,31–34]. The tests were performed with 5 x 2 cm adhesive tapes on coated and non-coated areas of brick samples ($n = 10$); and the amount of material released by the tape was expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Similarly, hardness tests operate on very small areas causing minimal damage. The measurements were performed with a Baxlo® Shore-A durometer equipped with calibration device ($n = 20$).

2.2.5. Water permeability tests

To complete the study, Karsten permeability tests were carried out on non-coated and coated samples. The Karsten tube is an open vertical device graduated from 0 to 4.5 ml, which is coupled with mastic to the tested surface. Contrary to capillary rise, the absorption occurs mainly because of the pressure exerted by the water column as occurs in rain driven by wind and gravity [35,36]. The permeability data were plotted as water absorbed, in grams per cm^2 , vs. the elapsed time, in minutes and linear regression analyses was used for evaluating permeability coefficients.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Non-coated bricks

3.1.1. Bonding and dimensions of bricks

The raw materials and basic steps to fabricate historical bricks are essentially the same as nowadays [37]. However, ancient bricks were usually handmade in wooden moulds and fired at relatively low temperatures leading to weaker pieces than modern ones. The visual inspection of the site revealed the bricks are fairly well preserved considering the age of the monumental ensemble (XII-XIII century). The brickwork consisted of alternating courses of stretchers and headers (Fig. 3), in which the exposed edge is the length and width of the brick respectively [37,38]. Several bricks were measured in the monument along their lengths ($n = 40$) and widths ($n = 80$) to obtain information about manufacturing steps (shaping). The average length was 27.7 ± 1.32 cm (RSD = 4.76%) and the width 13.4 ± 0.54 cm (RDS = 4.03%). The small dispersion found in lengths and widths of bricks suggests they were probably confectioned in moulds and compacted. As can be seen, the sizes satisfy well a known mathematical relationship in brickworks, by which the length of the brick is twice its width plus one standard joint of 1 cm [37].

3.1.2. XRD, XRF and TG-MS analyses

The diffractograms showed quartz, calcite, dolomite, halite, muscovite, diopside and gypsum (Fig. 4). Although carbonates decompose between 750 and 950 °C [39], the presence of calcite and dolomite does not necessarily mean the calcining temperatures were below 750 °C. If these temperatures were exceeded, the resulting oxides (CaO and MgO) may undergo hydration and carbonation reactions yielding the corresponding carbonates again. However, the absence of neoformed minerals as gehlenite and wollastonite indicates the calcining temperatures were not particularly high. Gehlenite, for instance, is formed in Ca-rich matrices [40] by decomposition of phyllosilicates at 800–850 °C [41,42]. The presence of minor proportions of gypsum and halite can be explained by capillary-assisted migration processes from nearby materials and specially, rammed walls showing efflorescence and located at the bottom of the brickwork.

Fig. 4. X-ray diffractogram of ancient brick studied in San Esteban.

TG-MS and XRF analyses provided a better understanding about chemical species present in ancient bricks. TG has high sensitivity for determining volatile substances that are identified by mass spectrometry (TG-MS) [43]. Moreover, TG is more reliable than XRF for low atomic number elements (Z), in which X-ray methods lack sensitivity. The elevated concentration of CaO found by XRF corroborates the calcareous nature of bricks (Fig. 5). In addition, the TG curve shows three decomposition steps that are attributed to H₂O, CO₂ and SO₃ as confirmed by MS. The first loss 1.7142% occurs between 100 and 200 °C and is assigned to non-combined water with a minor contribution of crystallisation water from gypsum (CaSO₄ 2H₂O). The absence of water fragments (m/z H₂O⁺ 18.03) within 200–400 °C points to lack of organic matter rests whose oxidation yields simultaneous release of CO₂ and H₂O. Therefore, the second step is due to CO₂ removal from dolomite and calcite previously identified by XRD. Stoichiometric calculations using TG and XRF data provided an estimation of 46.6% calcite and 13.1% dolomite. Finally, the third step is due to sulphates decomposition releasing SO₂ and ½O₂ as confirmed the m/z SO₃⁺ fragment. The low magnitude of the step is consistent with the small XRD peaks assigned to gypsum.

Fig. 5. Left: TG-MS analysis showing three decompositions associated to water, carbonates and calcium sulphate; Right: total volatile substances found by TG and rest of elements, expressed as oxides, determined by XRF.

3.1.3. Microscopy examination

The majority of decay processes occurring in building materials start on the surface and for that reason OM and SEM may reveal valuable information. OM images showed small cracks and rests of mortars adhered to the outer surface of bricks (Fig. 6a and b). Furthermore, the existence of pores and grainy textures found in SEM indicates the bricks were poorly calcined, as earlier discussed by analysis of XRD data (Fig. 6c and d). Appropriate firing conditions in modern bricks produce complete sintering of minerals and denser microstructures (Fig. 6e and f).

Fig. 6. OM and SEM images of ancient and modern brick samples: a) faced surface of ancient brick (70); b) rests of lime mortars in the bottom part (70); c) pore and grainy texture of ancient brick (500); d) texture showing deficient cohesion of brick components (1000); e) and f) texture of commercial tile brick showing absence of pores and better cohesion than ancient bricks (500 and 1000).

3.2. Consolidants

Contrary to sodium silicate, nanolime and ethyl silicate treatments use nanoparticles strategies to consolidate surfaces. Therefore, they were studied by TEM before applying on samples (Fig. 7). The nanolime suspensions are composed of hexagonal Ca(OH)_2 nanoparticles that are converted into calcite because of atmospheric CO_2 action [3,10]. The small hexagons form clusters and regular sonication is often needed to break down the floccules to stabilise the

suspension (Fig. 7a and b). The discrete nature of the nanoparticles causes the formation of discontinuous coatings usually detected by microscopy [11,31]. Besides, the irregular accumulation of nanolime may be assisted by surface defects (interfaces and pores) exerting higher suction on $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ nanoparticles [11].

In contrast to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Si}(\text{OEt})_4$ forms stable mixtures with organic solvents as ethanol or white spirit. The treatment was sprayed on Petri dishes and left to cure 15 days under laboratory conditions to produce the nanosilica phase (SiO_2) by hydration of $\text{Si}(\text{OEt})_4$. Next, the coating was softly removed with a spatula and sonicated in 2-propanol to prepare TEM samples. The silica phase remained agglomerated upon complete hydrolysis of $\text{Si}(\text{OEt})_4$ (Fig. 7c and d). The strong agglomeration along with the amorphous nature of silica made difficult the distinction of individual particles by TEM. Roughly speaking, the smallest and largest sizes of silica clusters varied between 20 and 500 nm. Hence, although ethyl silicate solutions are homogenous, the deposited nanosilica phase is susceptible to clustering and other phenomena as shrinking [44].

Fig. 7. TEM images of nanoparticles-based consolidants - a) and b) fresh crystalline $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ nanoparticles with an average size around 400 nm; c) and d) amorphous SiO_2 nanoparticles resulting from ethyl silicate hydrolysis after 15 days.

3.3. Coated-bricks

3.3.1. Surface distribution and chemistry of coatings

The nanolime coatings showed unequal distribution when sprayed on brick samples. The nanoparticles were mainly found on erodible zones (borders) as recently reported in porous materials [3,10,31]. Image segmentation is a practical tool for examining nanolime since its colour (white) differs considerably from the background (Fig. 8; left). The optical microscope is equipped with adjustable LEDs providing constant illumination and polariser filter to eliminate reflections. Once captured, the images were loaded into ImageJ software, converted into 8-bit and segmented by threshold operations using grey-scale histograms (Fig. 8; centre) [31]. The coating fraction was easily evaluated using binary images and represented 11.2–23.74% of the total examined area (Fig. 8; right).

Ethyl silicate formed imperceptible coatings giving minimal contrast with the background (Fig. 9a and b). Lastly, sodium silicate provided hard glassy coatings with an initial intense brightness due to water retained in the $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gel (Fig. 9c). The brightness dropped rapidly within 5–6 days and shortly after, thin cracks appeared. In the next days, the cracks continued to grow together with the occurrence of scaling and detachment events. The development of white patina altering the brick colour was another concern of the treatment (Fig. 9d). Similar deposits have been described in lime mortars, plasters and wall paintings consolidated with sodium silicate [45].

Fig. 8. Heterogeneous dispersion of nanolime; the coating is mainly accumulated in transition zones and surface defects. Left: OM images of coated bricks at several magnifications (67 and 186); Centre: coating segmentation (red) operated with ImageJ; Right: coating fraction (binary image) over the total area.

Fig. 9. OM images of coated bricks; a) and b) ethyl silicate at 65 and 190; c) non-polarised OM image of brick coated with sodium silicate (65); d) polarised image of the same sample revealing white patina (190).

The particular behaviour of sodium silicate coatings deserves a more detailed analysis. The coalescence and hardening of sodium silicate is favoured by water evaporation and capillary suction exerted by the surface. Yet, the polymerisation of silicate chains may play an important role in the rigidity of the film and the occurrence of cracks and scaling patterns. Chemically speaking, the polymerisation involves condensation of silicon-based tetrahedral units leading to a wide variety of chemical species as dimmers, trimmers and more polymerised structures. In addition, the high pH of the treatment aids CO_2 absorption and carbonation to occur (Na_2CO_3) [46]. Bearing this information in mind, a proposed sequence of reactions for sodium silicate coatings is shown below:

The Eq. (1) shows silica gel formation by hydrolysis of sodium silicate, where $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a simplified structure of the gel. In more detail, the alkaline conditions promote the hydrolysis of

tetra-coordinated silicon structures that are divided into oxohydroxo complexes (monomers) among which $[\text{SiO}_2(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{SiO}(\text{OH})_3]^-$ are stable forms at high pH (11–12). A slight pH decrease favours formation of dimmers, trimers, etcetera by monomers condensation through nucleophilic addition ($\text{S}_{\text{N}2}$ type). The condensation reaction is enabled by nucleophilic groups ($-\text{OH}$) of the oxo-hydroxo complexes and easy leaving molecules (H_2O) as usual in $\text{S}_{\text{N}2}$ reactions [47]. The rigidity of the coating can be affected by the relative amount of linear chains (Q^2 units) vs. cross-linking degree assisted by Q^3 and Q^4 connections. The Fig. 10 (left bottom) gives an example of possible species that are initially formed by condensation of oxo-hydroxo complexes in $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gels. The molecule owns cross-linking positions (Q^3) through which further condensation may operate connecting the chain with nearby ones (ramification). Certainly, equivalent positions within the chain may extend the links enabling creation of rigid 3D structures.

Fig. 10. Left top: $[\text{SiO}_2(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{SiO}(\text{OH})_3]^-$ monomers stable at high pH. The silicon atom (sp^3 hybridisation) is labelled as Q^0 as no other tetrahedrons are bonded to it; Left bottom: molecular chain formed by condensation of the above monomers. The Q^3 tetrahedron enables connection with nearby chains (cross-linking). Right: close chains retaining water molecules inside the gel by hydrogen bonding (Na^+ ions are not displayed).

The second reaction (2) shows the progressive dehydration of $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Certainly, the gel retains water due to inter-molecular bonding between H_2O molecules and neighbouring tetrahedrons of the polymeric structure (Fig. 10 – right). Finally, the third process (3) addresses the carbonation reaction responsible for white efflorescence formation on bricks. The dissolution of CO_2 is facilitated by the strong alkalinity of sodium silicate films (OH^-) and water entrapped

in the gel (Fig. 10 right). In the proposed mechanism the reactions may run simultaneously and therefore, polymerisation, coalescence and carbonation are probably overlapped in time.

SEM images revealed additional information about the treatments and corroborated OM findings. The nanolime treatment formed irregular CaCO_3 clusters illustrated at 2000x and 10000x magnifications in Fig. 11.a and .b [10]. Although the clusters had micrometric size, the individual CaCO_3 particles showed dimensions below the micrometric scale. Ethyl silicate formed irregular SiO_2 layers that were disseminated as platy structures on the surface (Fig. 11.c and .d) and similar morphologies to those found in TEM (Fig. 7). In sodium silicate coatings, SEM images, shown in Fig. 11.e and .f, confirmed cracks occurrence and revealed clearly scaling and detachment alterations. The efflorescence (patina) was discernible by SEM as a granular material deposited on the coating's surface. Actually, EDS measurements confirmed Si, O, Na and substantial amounts of C (up to 15.76%) because of sodium silicate carbonation (Na_2CO_3).

Fig. 11. SEM examination of coated samples; a) and b) nanolime coatings at 2000x and 10000x; c) and d) platy SiO₂ structures deposited by ethyl silicate at 2000x and 5000x; e) cracks, scaling and detachment of sodium silicate; f) EDS spectra confirming carbonation performed in e)

3.3.2. Colour variation

Colour tests performed on ancient bricks showed poor reliability because of intrinsic colour differences of the samples. Therefore, the tests were conducted on control ceramic surfaces

allowing more suitable analysis of the coatings' role in colour change. OM images showed heterogeneous deposition and whitening effect of nanolime in comparison with non-coated samples (Fig. 12.a and b). Ethyl silicate made the surface a bit darker than the control one (Fig. 12.c) and no external film-forming effects were detected as it was also reported by Franzoni et al. in coated bricks [48]. As regards sodium silicate, cracks, white dots, diffuse white patina and partial scaling were found again in control ceramic surfaces (Fig. 12.d).

Fig. 12. Coatings comparison by OM at 200; a) non-coated; b) nanolime-coated; c) ethyl silicate-coated and d) sodium silicate-coated sample.

The colorimetric study (Table 2), shows the surface lightness DL was increased in nanolime (4.05) due to the white colour of $Ca(OH)_2$. Also, white patina development on sodium silicate led to visible lightness increase (3.69). However, ethyl silicate darkened the surface a bit when compared to untreated samples (-1.99). This darkening might be explained by the oily nature of white spirit, which is often used as solvent in commercial TEOS solutions. As to overall colour variations DE induced by the coatings, the highest difference was found for sodium silicate (11.24) followed by nanolime (8.25) and ethyl silicate (2.24). The $CIEL^*C^*h^0$ data were calculated from a^* and b^* using the equations shown in section 2.4. Chroma (C^*) values dropped in all coated surfaces indicating they were duller than non-coated samples. It is important to note

that sodium silicate was initially transparent and bright, but became gradually more opaque and brittle as illustrates Fig. 13.

Table 2. Colour alteration provoked by nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate coatings.

CIE	Non-coated samples									Mean	ΔL	ΔE	ΔC
L	52.61	51.86	54.24	52.86	52.32	52.40	52.09	51.99	52.55 \pm 0.76	-	-	-	
a	25.02	24.90	24.75	24.9	25.03	25.17	25.24	25.28	25.04 \pm 0.18				
b	27.81	27.08	27.06	27.62	27.46	27.74	27.89	27.86	27.57 \pm 0.34				
C	37.41	36.79	36.67	37.19	37.16	37.46	37.62	37.62	37.24 \pm 0.36				
h	48.02	47.40	47.55	47.97	47.65	47.78	47.86	47.78	47.75 \pm 0.21				
CIE	Nanolime coating									Mean	ΔL	ΔE	ΔC
L	56.30	57.11	56.80	56.30	56.53	56.36	56.63	56.78	56.60 \pm 0.29	4.05	8.25	-6.91	
a	21.98	21.12	21.37	21.78	21.89	22.08	21.67	21.52	21.68 \pm 0.33				
b	21.58	20.23	20.54	21.3	21.61	21.94	21.33	21.15	21.21 \pm 0.57				
C	30.80	29.25	29.64	30.46	30.76	31.13	30.41	30.17	30.33 \pm 0.63				
h	44.48	43.77	43.87	44.36	44.63	44.82	44.55	44.50	44.37 \pm 0.37				
CIE	Ethyl silicate coating									Mean	ΔL	ΔE	ΔC
L	51.14	52.83	50.16	50.08	50.58	49.92	49.88	49.84	50.55 \pm 1.02	-1.99	2.24	-0.95	
a	24.69	25.07	24.59	24.53	24.66	24.72	24.54	24.58	24.67 \pm 0.17				
b	26.73	27.94	26.23	26.33	26.62	26.53	26.24	26.27	26.61 \pm 0.57				
C	36.39	37.54	35.95	35.99	36.29	36.26	35.93	35.98	36.29 \pm 0.54				
h	47.27	48.10	46.85	47.03	47.19	47.02	46.92	46.90	47.16 \pm 0.41				
CIE	Sodium silicate coating									Mean	ΔL	ΔE	ΔC
L	52.37	53.66	56.99	57.41	58.32	57.75	55.39	58.00	56.25 \pm 2.20	3.69	11.24	-10.31	
a	24.67	22.17	18.73	18.59	17.09	17.68	20.66	17.12	19.59 \pm 2.71				
b	26.44	21.74	17.09	16.99	14.85	15.49	19.72	15.29	18.45 \pm 4.00				
C	36.16	31.05	25.36	25.18	22.64	23.51	28.56	22.95	26.93 \pm 4.73				
h	46.98	44.44	42.38	42.43	40.99	41.22	43.67	41.77	42.99 \pm 1.99				

Fig. 13. Sodium silicate evolution over time; a) non-polarised and b) polarised image at 48 h; c) and d) same approach at 14 days; e) and f) after 28 days white deposits and cracks were found.

3.3.3. Peeling and hardness tests

The peeling tests (Fig. 14) confirmed the consolidants efficiency in reinforcing original brick samples. The peeling detected in control samples was $272 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, while nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate reduced peeling to $29 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, $38 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and $27 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. In other words, the amount of removed material was reduced by 89.3%, 86.0% and 90.1% using nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate, respectively. The performance of nanolime and ethyl silicate is consistent with previous impregnations carried out in earthen walls, stucco, stone and earthen

plasters [3,10,34,49]. Sodium silicate provided excellent performance despite the alteration patterns described in Fig. 9. A similar behaviour has been reported in abrasion tests conducted on concrete treated with sodium silicate [50].

The hardness tests did not reflect so clearly the strengthening action of coatings when compared to uncoated bricks (62.60 Shore-A). Moreover, little differences were found between nanolime (65 Shore-A), ethyl silicate (65.70 Shore-A) and sodium silicate (65.10 Shore-A). Nevertheless, t-student analyses confirmed the observed differences between non-treated and treated samples were statistically significant with a confidence interval of 95% ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 14. Peeling tests (top) and Shore-A hardness (bottom) of non-coated and coated bricks.

3.3.4. Water permeability tests

Karsten permeability data performed on coated bricks are shown in Fig. 15. Linear regression analysis, represented as dotted lines in the graph, proved that water permeability absorption was strongly correlated with time ($r^2 > 99.5\%$). In view of the slopes, neither nanolime nor sodium silicate caused any substantial effect on water permeability absorption. In contrast, ethyl silicate reduced water permeability as the slope dropped at a level of $0.0056 \text{ g/cm}^2\text{min}$, which represents 57.7% of that observed in control samples ($0.0097 \text{ g/cm}^2\text{min}$).

Fig. 15. Water permeability absorption of non-coated and coated samples.

4. Conclusions

This study assesses the pros and cons of nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate to consolidate heritage bricks dated in the XII-XIII century. The suitability of these consolidants is evaluated on the basis of chemical, mineral and microstructural features of original brick samples taken from the monument.

Finally, the paper also analyses the extent to which compositional and aesthetic values of bricks are correctly preserved using the consolidants. All things considered, the following conclusions can be drawn as a result of the investigation:

- The brickwork walls are relatively well-preserved and consist of alternate courses of stretchers and headers. Minor size variations along lengths and widths of bricks support the idea that they were confectioned by moulding.
- XRD, XRF and TG-MS data show the raw materials used to manufacture the bricks were mainly calcareous with an important fraction of calcite and dolomite. The absence of neoformed minerals as gehlenite indicates the manufacturing temperature did not exceed 800–850 °C.
- The analyses are also consistent with microstructural features observed by SEM and OM. Indeed, the examination of ancient bricks suggests they were manufactured at low temperatures since no glassy structures (vitrification) were observed.
- Although nanolime, ethyl silicate and sodium silicate provide similar consolidation performance, they also present strengths and limitations that are worth noting in heritage conservation.

Nanolime:

- The main advantage of nanolime resides in its chemical similarity with the studied samples because $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is transformed into a major component of the bricks (CaCO_3).
- It is important to stress that nanolime coatings perform at an excellent level considering the active concentration of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is clearly inferior to that of ethyl silicate or sodium silicate.
- The accumulation and heterogeneous distribution of nanolime in certain zones might be linked to the existence of surface defects that are generally more absorbent and mechanically weaker. The same behaviour has been recently confirmed in earthen materials [3,11]. Therefore, in addition to the intrinsic binding action of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, the coating's distribution may promote the effectiveness of nanolime.
- Although overall colorimetric values are not greatly affected by nanolime (ΔE), the colorimetric tests show important lightness variations (ΔL). This drawback must be carefully considered to preserve aesthetic values of bricks.

Ethyl silicate:

- Colour features are not significantly altered by ethyl silicate coatings. Visual, optical microscopy and colorimetric studies reveal a small darkening of samples coated with ethyl silicate.
- Ethyl silicate reduces water permeability if compared to nanolime, sodium silicate or non-coated samples. Clearly, water permeability reduction represents an important advantage of the coating in terms of rainwater resistance.
- The deposited phase by ethyl silicate (amorphous silica) is not similar to major minerals detected in bricks like quartz, carbonates and phyllosilicates. This raises doubts about long-term compatibility issues and the degree to which both materials (coating and substrate) may resist, as a whole, thermal and hydric cycles. Despite this, the analysis was performed on a limited number of pieces (bricks) and therefore, the existence of amorphous components cannot be completely excluded.

Sodium silicate:

- The chemistry of sodium silicate coatings is complex and affected by numerous factors, such as pH, $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ ratio, polymerisation degree and CO_2 absorption.
- Sodium silicate forms strong coatings, although in the short term susceptible to cracking and partial detachment when applied on bricks. Most likely, the rigidity of the film facilitates the occurrence of these cracks.

- Finally, sodium silicate has shown the highest overall colour variation (ΔE) among the studied consolidants. In this case, CO_2 absorption assisted by the high alkalinity of the film produces efflorescence formation (Na_2CO_3).

References

- [1] Practical Building Conservation, Earth, Brick & Terracotta, Ashgate, London, 2015s.
- [2] E. Sebastián, G. Cultrone, Technology of Rammed-Earth Constructions (“Tapial”) in Andalusia (Spain): Their Restoration and Conservation, In: M.B. Dan, R. Průkryl, Á. Török - (Eds) Materials, Technologies and Practice in Historic Heritage Structures, Springer, Dordrecht, 2010, pp. 11-28. DOI:10.1007/97890-481-2684-2_2.
- [3] M. Lanzón, V.D. Stefano, J.C.M. Gaitán, I.B. Cardiel, M.L. Gutiérrez-Carrillo, Characterisation of earthen walls in the Generalife (Alhambra): microstructural and physical changes induced by deposition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ nanoparticles in original and reconstructed samples, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 232 (2020) 117202, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.117202>.
- [4] ICOMOS 2nd International charter for the conservation and restoration of monuments and sites; the Venice charter, 1964.
- [5] E. Doehne, C.A. Price, *Stone Conservation an Overview of Current Research*, The Getty Conservation Institute, Los Angeles, California, 2010.
- [6] C. Price, K. Ross, G. White, A further appraisal of the ‘lime technique’ for limestone consolidation, using a radioactive tracer, *Stud. Conserv.* 33 (1988) 178–186, <https://doi.org/10.1179/sic.1988.33.4.178>.
- [7] V. Daniele, G. Taglieri, R. Quaresima, The nanolimes in Cultural Heritage conservation: characterisation and analysis of the carbonatation process, *J. Cult. Herit.* 9 (2008) 294–301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2007.10.007>.
- [8] L. Dei, B. Salvadori, Nanotechnology in cultural heritage conservation: nanometric slaked lime saves architectonic and artistic surfaces from decay, *J. Cult. Herit.* 7 (2006) 110–115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CULHER.2006.02.001>.
- [9] J. Otero, V. Starinieri, A.E. Charola, Influence of substrate pore structure and nanolime particle size on the effectiveness of nanolime treatments, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 209 (2019) 701–708, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.03.130>.
- [10] M. Lanzón, J.A. Madrid, A. Martínez-Arredondo, S. Mónaco, Use of diluted $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspensions and their transformation into nanostructured CaCO_3 coatings: a case study in strengthening heritage materials (stucco, adobe and stone), *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 424 (2017) 20–27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2017.02.248>.
- [11] M. Lanzón, V.E. García-Vera, A.J. Tenza-Abril, V. De Stefano, Use of image analysis to evaluate surface dispersion and covering performance of nanolime coatings sprayed on heritage material substrates, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 480 (2019) 962–968, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.03.066>.
- [12] D. R. Lide, ed., *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*, Internet Version, <<http://www.hbcpnetbase.com>>, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2005.
- [13] P. Baglioni, D. Chelazzi, R. Giorgi, E. Carretti, N. Toccafondi, Y. Jaidar, Commercial $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ nanoparticles for the consolidation of immovable works of art, *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.* 114 (2014) 723–732, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-013-7942-6>.
- [14] R. Giorgi, L. Dei, P. Baglioni, A new method for consolidating wall paintings based on dispersions of lime in alcohol, *Stud. Conserv.* 45 (2000) 154–161.
- [15] J. Otero, A.E. Charola, C.A. Grissom, V. Starinieri, An overview of nanolime as a consolidation method for calcareous substrates, *Ge-Conservacion* 1 (2017) 71–78.

- [16] Anna Arizzi, Luz Stella Gomez-Villalba, Paula Lopez-Arce, Giuseppe Cultrone, Rafael Fort, Lime mortar consolidation with nanostructured calcium hydroxide dispersions: the efficacy of different consolidating products for heritage conservation, *Eur. J. Mineral.* 27 (2015) 311–323, <https://doi.org/10.1127/ejm/2015/0027-2437>.
- [17] Valeria Daniele, Giuliana Taglieri, Nanolime suspensions applied on natural lithotypes: the influence of concentration and residual water content on carbonation process and on treatment effectiveness, *J. Cult. Herit.* 11 (2010) 102–106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2009.04.001>.
- [18] G. Borsoi, B. Lubelli, R. van Hees, R. Veiga, Silva A. Santos, L. Colla, L. Fedele, P. Tomasin, Effect of solvent on nanolime transport within limestone: how to improve in-depth deposition, *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 497 (2016) 171–181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2016.03.007>.
- [19] G. Borsoi, B. Lubelli, R. van Hees, R. Veiga, Silva A. Santos, Optimization of nanolime solvent for the consolidation of coarse porous limestone, *Appl. Phys. A* 122 (2016) 846, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-016-0382-3>.
- [20] P. López-Arce, L.S. Gomez-Villalba, L. Pinho, M.E. Fernández-Valle, M. Álvarez de Buergo, R. Fort, M. Álvarez de Buergo, R. Fort, Influence of porosity and relative humidity on consolidation of dolostone with calcium hydroxide nanoparticles: effectiveness assessment with non-destructive techniques, *Mater. Charact.* 61 (2010) 168–184, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2009.11.007>.
- [21] A. Zornoza-Indart, P. López-Arce, L. López-Polín, Durability of traditional and new nanoparticle based consolidating products for the treatment of archaeological stone tools: Chert artifacts from Atapuerca sites (Burgos, Spain), *J. Cult. Herit.* 24 (2017) 9–21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2016.10.019>.
- [22] Elisa Franzoni, Gabriela Graziani, Enrico Sassoni, Ginevra Bacilieri, Michele Griffa, Pietro Lura, Solvent-based ethyl silicate for stone consolidation: influence of the application technique on penetration depth, efficacy and pore occlusion, *Mater. Struct.* 48 (2015) 3503–3515, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-014-0417-1>.
- [23] A. Sierra-Fernández, L.S. Gómez-Villalba, M.E. Rabanal, R. Fort, New nanomaterials for applications in conservation and restoration of stony materials: A review, *Mater Constr* 67 (2017) 107. DOI:10.3989/mc.2017.07616.
- [24] Elisabetta Zendri, Guido Biscontin, Ilaria Nardini, Sara Riato, Characterization and reactivity of silicatic consolidants, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 21 (2007) 1098–1106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2006.01.006>.
- [25] F. Xu, W. Zeng, D. Li, Recent advance in alkoxy silane-based consolidants for stone, *Prog. Org. Coatings* 127 (2019) 45–54, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2018.11.003>.
- [26] A.P. Ferreira Pinto, J. Delgado Rodrigues, Impacts of consolidation procedures on colour and absorption kinetics of carbonate stone, *Stud. Conserv.* 59 (2014) 79–90, <https://doi.org/10.1179/2047058412Y.0000000075>.
- [27] G. Cultrone, V. Sánchez-Ibáñez, Consolidation with ethyl silicate: how the amount of product alters the physical properties of the bricks and affects their durability, *Mater. Constr.* 68 (332) (2018) 173, <https://doi.org/10.3989/mc.2018.12817>.
- [28] Zhiming Wang, Yuning Sun, Shuo Zhang, Yonglong Wang, Effect of sodium silicate on Portland cement/calcium aluminate cement/gypsum rich-water system: strength and microstructure, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 9993–10003, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA09901D>.
- [29] K.I. Marinakis, H.L. Shergold, Influence of sodium silicate addition on the adsorption of oleic acid by fluorite, calcite and barite, *Int. J. Miner. Process.* 14 (1985) 177–193, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-7516\(85\)90002-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-7516(85)90002-X).
- [30] H. Jansson, D. Bernin, K. Ramser, Silicate species of water glass and insights for alkali-activated green cement, *AIP Adv.* 5 (067167) (2015) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4923371>.
- [31] J.A. Madrid, M. Lanzón, Synthesis and morphological examination of highpurity Ca(OH)₂ nanoparticles suitable to consolidate porous surfaces, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 424 (2017) 2–8, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2017.03.210>.
- [32] ASTM, D 3359-02. Standard Test Methods for Measuring Adhesion by Tape Test, (2004).

- [33] M. Drdacky, J. Lesak, S. Rescic, Z. Slizkova, P. Tiano, J. Valach, Standardization of peeling tests for assessing the cohesion and consolidation characteristics of historic stone surfaces, *Mater. Struct.* 45 (2012) 505–520, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-011-9778-x>.
- [34] V.E. García-Vera, A.J. Tenza-Abril, M. Lanzón, The effectiveness of ethyl silicate as consolidating and protective coating to extend the durability of earthen plasters, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 236 (2020) 117445.
- [35] RILEM COMMISSION 25 PEM, Test No I.1 – Porosity accessible to water, *Mater. Constr. RILEM* 13. (1980) 177–179.
- [36] D. Vandevoorde, V. Cnudde, J. Dewanckele, L. Brabant, M. de Bouw, V. Meynen, E. Verhaeven, Validation of in situ applicable measuring techniques for analysis of the water absorption by stone, *Proc. Chem.* (2013) 317–327.
- [37] A. Lyons, *Materials for architects and builders: Fourth edition*, Taylor & Francis, London, 2010. DOI:10.4324/9780080949598.
- [38] EN 771-16:2011, Methods of test for masonry units - Part 16: Determination of dimensions, European Committee for Standardization (CEN); 2011.
- [39] M. Földvári, *Handbook of Thermogravimetric System of Minerals and its use in Geological Practice, Occasional Papers of Geological Institute of Hungary*, Budapest, 2011.
- [40] J.W. Anthony, R.A. Bideaux, K.W. Bladh, M.C. Nichols (Eds.), *Handbook of Mineralogy*, Mineralogical Society of America, Chantilly, VA 20151-1110, USA. <http://www.handbookofmineralogy.org/>.
- [41] P. López-Arce, J. García-Guinea, Weathering traces in ancient bricks from historic buildings, *Build. Environ.* 40 (2005) 929–941, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2004.08.027>.
- [42] P. López-Arce, J. García-Guinea, M. García, J. Obis, Bricks in historical buildings of Toledo City: characterisation and restoration, *Mater. Charact.* 50 (2003) 59– 68, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1044-5803\(03\)00101-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1044-5803(03)00101-3).
- [43] D.J. Morgan, Thermal analysis – including evolved gas analysis – of clay raw materials, *App. Clay Sci.* 8 (1993) 81–89, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-1317\(93\)90029-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-1317(93)90029-Z).
- [44] J. Brus, P. Kotlík, Cracking of organosilicone stone consolidants in gel form, *Stud. Conserv.* 41 (1996) 55–59.
- [45] A. Arnold, K. Zehnder, Monitoring Wall Paintings Affected by Soluble Salts – The Conservation of Wall Paintings, Proceedings of a symposium organized by the Courtauld Institute of Art and the Getty Conservation Institute, 1987.
- [46] M.T. Rodríguez, H. Pfeiffer, Sodium metasilicate (Na₂SiO₃): a thermo-kinetic analysis of its CO₂ chemical sorption, *Thermochim. Acta* 473 (2008) 92–95, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2008.04.022>.
- [47] Alain C. Pierre, in: *Introduction to Sol-Gel Processing*, second ed., Springer, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38144-8>.
- [48] E. Franzoni, B. Pigino, A. Leemann, P. Lura, Use of TEOS for fired-clay bricks consolidation, *Mater. Struct.* 47 (2014) 1175–1184, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-013-0120-7>.
- [49] V.E. García-Vera, A.J. Tenza-Abril, A.M. Solak, M. Lanzón, Calcium hydroxide nanoparticles coatings applied on cultural heritage materials: their influence on physical characteristics of earthen plasters, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 504 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2019.144195> 144195.
- [50] E. Franzoni, B. Pigino, C. Pistolesi, Ethyl silicate for surface protection of concrete: performance in comparison with other inorganic surface treatments, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 44 (2013) 69–76, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2013.05.008>